

Gryon nixon Masner, female, dorsal view with right (fore and hind) wings removed (a) and side view (b).

After 4 days' exposure in the field, the eggs were incubated in the laboratory in small, sealed, glass vials with moisture provided in a wad of cotton.

Parasitization was probably higher in the continuously cropped fields (16 and 29%) than in the biannually cropped fields (4 and 18%) (see table).

The scelionid parasite, identified by the senior author as *Gryon nixon* Masner (= *Hadronotus flavipes* Ashmead and *leptocorisae* Nixon), is also recorded in India, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Papua New Guinea. The adult is 1.25 mm long and black except for hyaline wings, yellow-brown legs, reddish to dark brown antennae, coxae, and tarsal segment V, and with a pale yellow stigmal vein (see figure). ■

Pest management and control WEEDS

Plant height as a varietal characteristic in reducing weed competition in rice

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The extent of weed infestation in rice fields is influenced by factors such as degree of land preparation, water management, fertilizer application, seeding method, and plant density.

Taller plant types generally are considered more efficient than shorter plant types in suppressing weed growth because they grow rapidly and shade the weeds. To determine the extent of yield reduction caused by weeds in rice varieties of different plant heights, experiments were conducted in 1979 transplanted aman and 1979-80 boro seasons at the main station of BRRI. The experiments were in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

In the t. aman season, the highest yield was obtained from BR4, followed

Yield reduction caused by weeds in rice cultivars of different heights, in 2 seasons at BRRI, Dacca, Bangladesh.^a

Variety	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Yield reduction (%)
		Unweeded check	Weed-free	
1979 t. aman season				
Nizersail	154	2.96 a	3.21 a	7.19
BR4	120	3.19 a	3.65 a	12.60
BR6	97.5	2.03 a	2.71 b	25.09
1979-80 boro season				
Habiganj Boro VI	106.5	1.94 a	2.36 a	17.80
BR9	98	2.40 a	3.06 a	21.57
Chandina	62.4	2.54 a	3.49 b	27.22

^a Av of 3 replications. In a row, means followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

by Nizersail and BR6, in both unweeded and weed-free conditions (see table). The relative yield performance of the three varieties was not influenced by weed infestation. However, the yield reduction from weeds increased with decrease in plant height. The yield reduction from weeds was 0.25 t/ha in the tallest variety Nizersail and 0.46 t, ha in BR4 with intermediate plant height. These reductions were not significant. But in the shortest variety BR6, the yield reduction of 0.68 t/ha was significant.

In the boro season (see table), the

trend was similar. The highest and significant yield reduction (0.95 t/ha) from weeds was in the shortest variety, Chandina. The yield reduction decreased with increasing plant height.

The relative yields of different rice varieties may not be changed by weed competition. The potential yields are reduced by weeds, more in the shorter, high yielding varieties than in the relatively taller local varieties. This finding indicates more benefits from weeding in high yielding varieties than in the local varieties. ■